

Education – A Means for Social and Political Emancipation

N. Devula

Research Scholar
Department of Political Science
Osmania University

Abstract:

The primary topic of this study centres on the opinions of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar regarding Education, as well as his unwavering belief in the fundamental concepts of education, unity, and struggle. According to Ambedkar, education is widely acknowledged as the most efficacious means of eliminating social oppression and enabling marginalized individuals to attain social progress, economic enhancement, and political emancipation. Education has been identified as a fundamental requirement for the process of society reconstruction, which is founded upon the values of equality and justice. After analyzing the development of education in Indian society, it became evident that access to education was restricted to those from higher castes, both during the rule of Peshwa in Maharashtra and in the earlier period of the British Raj. He promoted the idea of providing education to all individuals, irrespective of their caste and gender. The individual voiced their participation in the financial deliberation, emphasizing the importance of ensuring universal access to education. A method based on quid pro quo is not suitable for the education department.

Enhancing the affordability of education should be pursued using diverse strategies and to the fullest degree possible. He demonstrated significant engagement in the deliberation process about the Bombay University Act and the Primary Education Amendment Bill, providing his insights and viewpoints on the subject of educational reform. The researcher founded the People's Education Society and developed educational facilities in the cities of Bombay and Aurangabad. He continuously underscored to the government the imperative of guaranteeing equitable educational opportunities for all citizens, devoid of any manifestation of prejudice. Nevertheless, he suggested that it is imperative to provide males and girls with separate educational opportunities. The objective of this study is to examine the viewpoints of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar toward education, with a particular emphasis on the adoption of a standardized education system in India.

Key Words: education, unity, struggle, equality, justice, higher caste, social oppression, social injustice etc.

Introduction

The original phrasing of his well-known slogan, Ambedkar advocated the notion that education served as the primary means of enhancing the socioeconomic standing of individuals. The catchphrase employed by the individual was "Educate, unite, struggle." The well-known slogan he is associated with is "Educate."

Ambedkar made significant intellectual contributions to the field of education with his testimony at the Indian Statutory Commission in the Bombay Presidency, which focused on the "State of Education of the Dalits." The aforementioned deposition is especially featured in Volume 4 of the compilation entitled "Dr. Ambedkar: Sampoorana Vangmay." In addition, the

article titled "Subsidy for Education" authored by him has been included in the Sampoorna Vangmay (Volume 3) of Dr Ambedkar's work. This article is based on his speech delivered to the Bombay Legislative Council on 12 March 1927, in which he called for increased government support for education and underscored the importance of providing cheap education to marginalized populations. In Volume 19, the book titled "Dr Ambedkar: Sampoorna Vangmay" delves into several challenges faced by the Scheduled Castes (SCs), notably their concerns about education.

The aforementioned concerns can be classified into two distinct categories: "insufficient backing for tertiary education" and "insufficient provisions for vocational instruction".

The Struggle of Dr Ambedkar for Education in Dalits

The subject of freedom frequently fails to acknowledge the importance of Dalit liberation. In the foreseeable future, we shall observe the anniversary of our emancipation from British colonial domination. The present moment is a favourable occasion to tackle the matter of Dalit liberation. Ambedkar ultimately rescued the Dalits from a system of double servitude. On November 12, 1930, the British Government, under the profound influence of Gandhiji's Civil Disobedience Movement, convened a Round Table Conference in London. During the conference, a young lawyer surprised everyone by refusing to acknowledge Gandhiji as the ultimate leader of the entire Indian populace. His name was Dr. B.R. Ambedkar. As per his assertion, a significant proportion of Congress officials maintained the conviction in caste-based bias and exhibited reluctance in allowing Dalits any involvement in constitutional processes. Therefore, he proposed that it was crucial to construct separate electorates consisting solely of Dalit candidates and electors.

The Communal Award was issued by British Prime Minister Ramsay Macdonald on 6 August 1932. This award recognized the Dalits as distinct from the Hindus and established a separate electorate for them. Mahatma Gandhi was held in custody at the Poona prison during that time. This disclosure was interpreted by him as an attempt to alienate Dalits from the Hindu community. Mahatma Gandhi commenced a fast-unto-death on September 20, 1932, as a means of protesting against the Communal Award, resulting in substantial turmoil throughout the country. Dr. Ambedkar was summoned to safeguard the life of Mahatma Gandhi. Ambedkar succumbed to increasing pressure from different groups and agreed to a compromise, with the condition that reservations be made for the Dalits at all levels of society. Gandhiji acquiesced and subsequently terminated his fast on September 26th.

In the later half of the 19th century, social reformers employed their literary works to launch a vigorous challenge of Brahmanical practices. Jotirao Phule's Gulamgiri was one of them. The opposition to the Varna system in the southern region was stated by Periyar and Narayan Guru. After several decades, Ambedkar was bestowed with the responsibility of crafting the Constitution of the recently liberated India, recognizing his remarkable credentials and scholastic contributions. He took on the role of the country's first law minister. Over time, Ambedkar's ideas have become increasingly significant.

Before attaining independence, he was recognized as a jurist with remarkable intellectual prowess. On 12 March 1927, the speaker presented pertinent inquiries concerning the role of education within Indian society during his address to the Bombay Legislative

Council. The individual conveyed a deep sense of concern regarding the educational inadequacy in India.

Research released by the Government of India has indicated that if the present rate of educational progress persists, it would necessitate 40 years for boys and 300 years for girls of school-going age to get an education. Dr. Ambedkar voiced apprehension regarding the divergent goals pursued by two departments within the executive branch. The primary aim of the Department of Education is to facilitate the cultivation of moral and social growth in individuals. In contrast, the Department of Excise operates in a contrary manner. Sir, I contend that it is justifiable to advocate for the allocation of a comparable sum of cash to the education sector as the existing amount received from the public through excise income. In this particular presidency, the per capita spending on education is a modest 14 annas, whereas the corresponding excise income earned is Rs 2.17 [35 annas]. I contend that it is just and fair that our allocation of funds towards education should be commensurate with the revenue generated through taxation.[1] In contemporary times, there is a growing need for enhanced financial resources in the field of education, not only among students but also among other advocacy groups. In this context, the concepts put forth by Ambedkar can offer useful insights and guidance.

During the argument, Dr. Ambedkar expressed another issue, highlighting the significant wastage of monies allocated to elementary education. The primary goal of primary education is to guarantee that every child who enters primary school acquires literacy skills and sustains literacy from birth. Upon analyzing the statistics, it becomes apparent that only 18.5% of students who commence primary school can attain success in the fourth grade. Eighty-two out of every one hundred children, constituting the remaining 82, revert to a state of illiteracy.[2]

The matter of school dropouts continues unmitigated. The issue in question has been earlier understood by Dr. Ambedkar. The individual concluded that only providing education to a youngster was inadequate. Ensuring their ongoing attendance in school till they have finished their elementary education is of utmost importance. Merely engaging in the act of planting a seedling is inadequate. Furthermore, it is crucial to ensure that it is supplied with sufficient water and fertilizers to mitigate the risk of premature mortality. Therefore, Ambedkar urged the respected education minister to give extra funding towards primary education, to ensure that their spending produces concrete results.

Additionally, Dr. Ambedkar directed his attention towards the phenomena of commoditization within the realm of education. Based on an analysis of the statistics about the allocation of funds for education during the current president, it is apparent that fees account for around 36 per cent of the overall expenditures for art colleges, 31 per cent of the expenditures for high schools, and 26 per cent of the expenditures for middle schools. I therefore claim that the phenomenon being mentioned is the process of making education a commercial product. It is vital to guarantee the accessibility of education for all individuals. As a result of Dr Ambedkar's deep-seated apprehension for the socioeconomically disadvantaged segments of society, he articulated, "The present juncture marks the initiation of secondary education, intermediate education, and tertiary education for the lower classes." Hence, this

department must prioritize the accessibility of higher education for individuals belonging to lower socioeconomic strata.

He mentions another notable issue: "The census report of this administration has classified the entire population into four separate categories to assess the educational advancement of different communities." The first classification is commonly denoted as "advanced Hindus," while the second classification is commonly referred to as "intermediate Hindus." This classification pertains to individuals who have been formally designated as non-Brahmins, notably Marathas and related castes, due to political considerations. The backward classes pertain to a specific classification that includes individuals from the depressed classes, Hill Tribes, and Criminal Tribes. Following this, the fourth category is associated with the Mahomedans. Upon careful examination of these disparities, it becomes apparent that there is a notable divergence in the educational advancements of these various communities.[4] Dr. Ambedkar's main emphasis was on addressing the disparities that were widespread in Indian society. As to his assertion, the nation consists of a multitude of heterogeneous communities. These municipalities demonstrate differences in their social status and progress. From an economic and sociological standpoint, one could suggest that disadvantaged social classes encounter distinct disadvantages that set them apart from other communities. Therefore, I contend that the concept of preferential treatment ought to be applied in their particular circumstances. The Mahomedans' standing is relatively inferior to that of the backward classes, as evidenced. My only contention is that if the Government is to provide preferred care to those who are deserving and in the most dire need, then the Mahomedans should be given less attention.

Dr. Ambedkar's views on education aligned with the regional, societal, and economic circumstances of India, and were based on scientific reasoning.

'Teach, unite, fight'

Despite Dr Ambedkar's significant contributions to the subject of education since the foundation of the Hitkarini Sabha in 1924, there is a dearth of scholarly research on his ideas on education. One of the objectives of the Sabha was to facilitate the provision of education to a growing population of disadvantaged groups. To accomplish this, the Sabha established numerous educational institutions, accommodations, libraries, and bookstores. The launch of a monthly publication named Saraswati Belas was undertaken by the students, under the direction of the Sabha. In the year 1935, the Sabha established temporary accommodations in Sholapur and Belgaun, alongside a complimentary reading facility, a hockey association, and two temporary accommodations in Bombay. Dr. Ambedkar founded the Depressed Classes Educational Society in 1928. In 1945, he founded the Lok Shaikshik Samaj to guarantee higher education opportunities for the disadvantaged segments of society. The organization mentioned earlier took the initiative to build multiple colleges and middle schools. Furthermore, it offered monetary assistance to dormitories. Essentially, the Lok Shaikshik Samaj had a substantial impact on making higher education more accessible to the Dalit population.

The literary writings of Dr Ambedkar covered a diverse array of topics, including economics, law, the Constitution, political science, sociology, philosophy, religion, anthropology, and various others. Moreover, his persistent captivation with the field of

education was apparent. It surpassed mere conjecture. He endeavoured to express his viewpoints pragmatically.

The well-known slogan he is associated with is "Educate." Education plays an undeniable role in forming the character and consciousness of individuals. Class unity can solely be attained through the possession of a substantial level of education and a comprehensive understanding of one's class interests. Education propels an individual onto a path of hardship. Dr. Ambedkar asserts that education has a pivotal role in promoting courage, conveying the significance of unity, nurturing consciousness of one's entitlements, and inspiring citizens to actively champion their rights. He possessed the conviction that education is a dynamic process of advancement. If it does not succeed in attaining its objectives, it becomes ineffective. According to Dr. Ambedkar, education that does not possess the capacity to empower individuals and convey ideals of equality and morality is not considered authentic education. Genuine education cultivates the human species, establishes pathways for nourishment, imparts information, and promotes a feeling of egalitarianism. Education has a significant role in revitalizing society.

The aims and goals of education

The foundational principles of Ambedkar's social-philosophical ideas were rooted in the concept of egalitarianism. The focal point of his social ideology centred on the fundamental tenets of human dignity and self-esteem. The individual aimed to employ education as a mechanism for cultivating concepts of justice, equality, fraternity, freedom, and fearlessness inside the societal framework. He aspired to replace a society founded on ancestry with one founded on principles. Education is undeniably the only method via which these moral concepts may be promoted.

The intellectual framework of Ambedkar was significantly influenced by Buddhist concepts, and he advocated for the development of moral ideals among individuals. As per his assertion, the importance of education resides exclusively in its capacity to enhance the welfare and success of individuals, as well as the progress of society. Furthermore, he promoted the idea of harmonizing education and employment. Educational attainment has a key role in cultivating societal stability. Exemplary conduct and appropriate behaviour are derived from the use of rational thought, a cognitive process that can only be achieved through formal education, practical experience, and meaningful interpersonal exchanges. Ambedkar's educational objectives were aligned with his wider economic, social, and political ambitions. He demonstrated a strong commitment to promoting the virtues of logical and scientific education.

With the deadline approaching, the education minister at the time, MC Chagla, stated that the intention of our Constitutional framers was not for us to merely create slums, relocate students there, assign unqualified teachers, provide them with insufficient textbooks, and lack playgrounds, and then claim that we have followed Article 45 and that primary education is expanding... MC Chagla (1964) aimed to offer authentic education to children between the ages of 6 and 14.

. The Right to Education Act (RTE) as a legislative policy

The legal legislation enacted by the Parliament of India on August 4, 2009, is commonly referred to as the Right to Education Act (RTE), or the Right of Children to Free and

Compulsory Education Act. This legislation delineates the importance of ensuring that children between the ages of 6 and 14 in India receive free and mandatory education, as stipulated by Article 21a of the Indian Constitution. India became a member of the group of 135 countries that have recognized education as a fundamental right for all children, after the enactment of the Act on April 1, 2010.

The legislation mandates education as a fundamental right for all children between the ages of 6 and 14 and delineates the fundamental criteria for primary schools. Private schools have a legal obligation to give 25% of their available seats to students, and as part of the public-private partnership policy, the state provides reimbursement for this allocation. Private schools admit children based on their socioeconomic status or reservations based on caste. Furthermore, it prohibits the functioning of any educational institutions that lack official recognition and specifies that there will be no remuneration for contributions or financial support, and no assessments will be carried out with the child or parent for admission. The Act explicitly forbids the detention, expulsion, or compulsory administration of a board examination to any kid until they have completed their primary school. Furthermore, there is a framework in place to facilitate the execution of targeted training initiatives to elevate school dropouts to the same educational level as their counterparts within the same age group.

Education serves as a powerful tool via which individuals who face economic and social disadvantages can transcend poverty and actively participate in societal affairs.

India is home to around 19% of the world's child population. This suggests that India has the largest number of young individuals worldwide, which is a largely favourable situation, especially when compared to countries like China, which have a growing elderly population.

Unfortunately, India is home to around one-third of the world's population that lacks literacy skills. The levels of literacy have shown an upward trend, albeit with a notable deceleration in the rate of this growth. For example, the literacy rate experienced a 12.6% growth from 1991 to 2001, but it has already declined to 9.21%.

At now, there exist legal channels through which the state can be held accountable for its understanding of student 'rights'. However, as stated before, these locations alone are insufficient to exert influence, and they only recognize the rights of those who are already 'included'. The education guarantee initiatives, exemplified by the ongoing implementation in Madhya Pradesh and the subsequent statewide commitment under the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, are designed to address the need for schools in underserved regions. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that the categorization of schools, their calibre, and the educational material they provide are not susceptible to citizen intervention and are solely governed by the state. The increasing influx of donor funding into the state, along with the implementation of sector and sub-sector techniques to centralize policy areas, poses a possible risk of reinforcing the state's authority over civil society and other entities, while simultaneously reducing transparency. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have had a substantial impact on the progress of education, especially in recent times. Nevertheless, a significant number of their educational models are being directly integrated into state programs without undergoing a comprehensive evaluation of the advantages and perspectives they provide in formulating localized education plans that prioritize community ownership. Although the term 'community involvement' is increasingly being used in state programs, there is a dearth of initiatives aimed

at addressing the root reasons of inequality that impede the most marginalized individuals from expressing their viewpoints (see Subrahmanian, forthcoming). Village Education Committees (VECs) are commonly acknowledged as a new form of community involvement in education. However, they often display bureaucratic traits that prioritize the responsibility of identifying and accompanying children to school, rather than actively soliciting parental input on educational content and delivery.

The Right to Education Act

Article 21-A and the Right to Education Act were put into effect on April 1, 2010. The title of the Right to Education (RTE) Act incorporates the phrase 'free and compulsory'. The concept of 'free education' pertains to the stipulation that all children, except those admitted by their parents to a school lacking government backing, shall not be obligated to bear any fees, charges, or expenses that may impede their access to and completion of primary education. The notion of 'compulsory education' entails a duty on the pertinent governmental and municipal bodies to ensure the provision, attendance, and academic achievement of primary education for all children aged 6 to 14. India has made significant strides in establishing a rights-based system that places a legal obligation on both the Central and State Governments to uphold the fundamental rights of children, as delineated in Article 21A of the Constitution, in conjunction with the stipulations of the Right to Education Act.

The RTE Act encompasses provisions for:

The provision of compulsory and cost-free education to children until they have finished their elementary education at a nearby educational institution.

The concept of 'compulsory education' pertains to the obligation of the pertinent governing body to provide cost-free primary education and ensure obligatory admission, attendance, and graduation of elementary school for all individuals aged six to fourteen. The phrase 'free' pertains to the state in which a kid is exempt from any financial obligations, fees, or costs that may impede their capacity to engage in and complete primary education.

It enables the inclusion of a kid who has not been admitted to an age-appropriate class.

The paper outlines the responsibilities and functions of pertinent governmental entities, local authorities, and parents in guaranteeing the delivery of education that is both cost-free and obligatory. Furthermore, the document delineates the allocation of financial and other obligations between the Central and State Governments.

The paper outlines the norms and criteria for several issues, such as pupil-pupil-teacher ratios (PTRs), physical facilities and infrastructure, school working days, and teacher working hours.

Ensuring that the designated pupil-to-teacher ratio is maintained for each school, rather than being exclusively based on the average for the State, District, or Block, enables the effective distribution of teachers. This measure guarantees the absence of divergence in teacher roles between urban and rural regions. Furthermore, the legislation incorporates clauses that prohibit the utilization of educators for non-academic objectives, thereby barring tasks such as conducting annual censuses, engaging in elections for local governing bodies, state legislatures, and parliament, as well as doing disaster relief operations.

It simplifies the process of choosing appropriately qualified teachers, particularly those who have the required qualifications and academic qualifications.

The act comprises many elements, which involve the prohibition of physical punishment and mental harassment, screening techniques for child admission, capitation fees, private guidance provided by teachers, and the operation of schools lacking official accreditation.

The curriculum is specifically crafted to conform to the principles stated in the Constitution and foster the holistic growth of the kid. The primary objective is to augment the child's cognitive abilities, aptitude, and aptitude, while concurrently safeguarding their well-being from apprehension, distress, and unease. This objective is accomplished by implementing a learning system that is both child-friendly and child-centred.

Conclusion

Every subsequent generation harbours the ambition to build a nation that surpasses the present condition. Therefore, every country must provide utmost importance to education to empower the future generation. The achievement of the right to education on a national scale is commonly recognized to be dependent on the enforcement of mandatory education, particularly through the provision of free compulsory primary education. However, the goal of creating an educational system in India that guarantees inclusive access, equitable opportunities, and excellent education has not been achieved, mostly because of widespread poverty and societal prejudices. One other source of worry pertains to the limited capacity to evaluate dropout rates among marginalized communities.

References

1. <http://righttoeducation.in/know-your-rte/about>
2. <https://www.forwardpress.in/2017/10/ambedkars-thoughts-on-education-an-overview/>
3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322695770_DrBR_Ambedkar's_views_on_Education
4. https://www.google.com/search?q=ambedkar+vision+on+education&rlz=1C1CHBF_enIN862IN862&oq=ambedkar+vision+on+education&aqs=chrome..69i57.14242j0j4&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8
5. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/B._R._Ambedkar
6. <http://www.legalservicesindia.com/article/1925/Right-to-Education.html>